

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF PAIN MANAGEMENT IN POST-
OPERATIVE CASES USING DIFFERENT SCALES AND
QUESTIONNAIRES**¹Mudasir Maqbool, ²Dr. Sehrish Javed, ³Aqeel Ahmed Bajwa¹Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Kashmir., ²Women Medical Officer,
BHU Warn Sheikhpura., ³Scunthorpe General Hospital UK**Abstract**

Postoperative pain is one of the most common therapeutic issues in patients admitted in hospital and it can lead to increase in morbidity. Various studies regarding prevalence of Postoperative (PO) pain in tertiary care hospitals represent above 50% in first 24 hrs after surgery and above 30% in next 24 hrs after surgery. A comparative study of prevalence of post PO pain in different resource settings has shown that PO pain management (PM) requires the involvement of the anesthesiologists, surgeons, physicians and patient. Assessment of pain and its correlation with LOS of patient is important factor regarding treatment and recovery of patient. There is no separate and absolute method to determine level of pain and Length of stay (LOS) of patient specifically and separately. Along with assessment on scales, there are some other methods based on well design questionnaire. Some of those questionnaires are "The McGill Pain Questionnaire", "Pain Impact Questionnaire", and pain questionnaire developed by "The American Pain Society Quality of Care Committee". Etc. in this review, we will briefly see about the various Scales and Questionnaires used in Assessment of Pain management in post-operative cases.

Keywords: Postoperative pain, management, The McGill Pain Questionnaire, The American Pain Society Quality of Care Committee.

Corresponding author:**Mudasir Maqbool,**

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Kashmir.

QR code

Please cite this article in press **Mudasir Maqbool et al., Assessment of Pain Management In Post-Operative Cases Using Different Scales And Questionnaires., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(01).**

INTRODUCTION:

Postoperative pain is one of the most commonly seen therapeutic problems in patients admitted in hospital and it can increase morbidity.[1-8] Various studies regarding prevalence of Postoperative pain in tertiary care hospitals represent above 50% in first 24 hours after surgery and above 30% in next 24 hours after surgery.[9] A comparative study of prevalence of post Postoperative pain in different resource settings has shown that Postoperative pain management requires the involvement of the anesthesiologists, surgeons, physicians and patient.[9] As the effect of general anaesthesia in upper abdominal and also in thoracic surgery, reduction of breathing suppression and cough suppression can increase sensation of pain and also facilitating retained pulmonary secretion and pneumonia but regional anaesthesia has no such kind of effect which could be merge with Postoperative pain.[10] Postoperative pain can lead to delay in normal gastric and bowel function [11], thus contributing to a longer recovery period.[12] Pain is not an unavoidable consequence of surgery. In the majority of patients Postoperative pain is preventable with adequate analgesics and by use of appropriate newer techniques.[2-8,12,13] Despite this, a number of studies and surveys have shown a high prevalence of significant pain after surgery.[14-20] The recognition of the inadequacy of Postoperative Pain Management has prompted the development of corrective efforts by anaesthesiologist,

surgeons,[5,9,21-23] and Pain Management groups.[2,3,24-26] Assessment of pain and its correlation with LOS of patient is important factor regarding treatment and recovery of patient.[12] There is no separate and distinguished method to determine level of pain and LOS of patient specifically and separately. Along with assessment on scales, there are other methods based on well design questionnaire. Some of those questionnaires are “The McGill Pain Questionnaire” [32], “Pain Impact Questionnaire”[33], and pain questionnaire developed by “The American Pain Society Quality of Care Committee”.[34-36]

ASSESSMENT OF INTENSITY OF PAIN:

Assessment of intensity of pain is subjective phenomenon related with individual patient thoughts about pain. Its objective or absolute measurement is not possible with high accuracy and precision, although it is very necessary approach for selection of appropriate or most effective analgesic medication, its dose and duration of treatment. Pain assessment tools are mainly used in questionnaire based form or scale types. Scales are further subdivided into self-reporting, observational and psychological data according to mode of data collection.[37-39] Three widely use scales are Numeric Rating Scale (NRS) [37], Visual Analog Scale (VAS) [38] and Verbal Rating Scale (VRS) [Figure1] [35, 40].

Figure 1 Commonly use one dimensional scale represents NRS, VRS and VAS together [32]. Validity of VRS is not found significant and not comprise and use as substitute of NRS and VAS and mostly use only for nonparametric analysis.[33] They function best for the patient's subjective feeling of the intensity of pain right now—present PI. They may be used for worst, least, or average pain over the last 24 h, or during the last week. There are some limitations with this, as memory of pain is not accurate and often coloured by changing context factors.[34, 35, 36].

VALIDATION OF SCALES:

The NRS and the VAS scales have shown almost identical values in the same patient at different times after surgery, although the four point VRS seemed to underestimate the most intense pain compared with the VAS.[35] For younger children, from about 3 year, pain scales with happy and unhappy faces are well validated, for example, the faces pain scale.[34] Bijur et al. (2003) obtained a significant correlation between the VAS and the NRS ($r = 0.94$, 95% CI = 0.93-0.95) with the slope of the regression line 1.01 (95% CI = 0.97-1.06) indicating a strong level of agreement between the two tools.[42] De Loach et al. (1998) also found high correlation in postoperative patients between the VAS and the NRS although, the regression line slopes were 0.86 and 0.95 suggesting that the two scales do not agree.[43] This tells us that at best the VAS and the NRS provide similar information about pain, but a direct conversion cannot be made between them.[41] New research by Brewer [44], Sitepu [45], Wang and Keck [46], Zohu [47] regarding validation of VAS and NRS are done by many researchers not only for particular human species with specific kind of hospital setting but globally accepted all around the world. Zohu [47] reported high validity and reliability of VAS and NRS for Asian and Chinese patients. [48] The ability to assess pain outcomes is critical to improving pain management. Traditionally, the assessment of pain outcomes has been conducted by measuring each patient's subjective level of pain intensity scales. The American Pain Society Quality of Care Committee first developed quality improvement guidelines and programs to improve the treatment outcomes of patients with acute pain and cancer pain.

LOS OF PATIENTS WITH RESPECTED TO PM:

This scale is not solely used for multifaceted approaches to pain management, which should not only include the concept of proper PM but also

patient satisfaction with treatment of pain.[49] Recent studies reported interesting contradictory evidences regarding the association between patient satisfaction and pain. In a study of 2012 conducted in surgical unit it was concluded that the odds of patient satisfaction were 4.86 times if pain was controlled and 9.92 times if the patient were satisfied with efforts of health care team to PM .[50] Pellino and Ward [51] reported interestingly puzzling and inverse relationship between pain and satisfaction. Donovan reported that 86% patients were satisfied with their pain management whereas 75% of them reported significant pain. Similarly Chung and Lui also reported 85% of postoperative patients reported mild, moderate or severe pain, while 65% among them were satisfied with the pain management they received. Weis et al[52-54] investigated that although 43% of patients rated their pain as moderate to severe, 75% of patients were satisfied with their PM. Most of recent studies evaluating patient pain in different types of surgery report similar trends that the most of the patients reported that they were satisfied with the pain management they received while reported high level of pain they felt [55-59].

CONCLUSION:

Although, Pain Management is below the average for patients bearing severe pain in tertiary care hospital still high prevalence of mild and moderate pain is common. Satisfaction of patients is based on sociologically on behaviour of health care team, physically on betterment of treatment or surgery for which patient went through and psychologically cost of treatment which is one of the most important contributing factor in developing country like India where medical expenditure is one of the financial burden for below than middle class family. So pain rating scale should integrate with socio-economical status of patient to investigate the LOS and multidisciplinary, multi-drugs combination therapy should apply, for much better PM.

REFERENCES:

1. Donovan M, Dillon P, McGuier L. Incidence and charecteristics of pain in sample of medical-surgical inpatients. Pain 1987;30:69-78.
2. Agency for Health Care Policy and Research. Acute pain management: operative or medical procedures and trauma, part 1. Ciln Pharm 1992;11:309-514.
3. Agency for Health Care Policy and Research. Acute pain management: operative or medical procedures and trauma, part 2. Clin Pharm 1992;11:391-414.
4. Canellas M, Bosch F, Bassols A, Rue M, Banos

- JE. Prevalence of pain in hospitalized patients. *Med Clin (Barc)* 1993;101:51-4. [google translator,Spanish]
5. Royal College of Surgeons of England and College of Anesthetists` Comission on the Provision of Surgical Services. Report of the Working Party on Pain After Surgery London: Royal College of Surgeons 1990.
 6. Bruster S, Jarman B, Bosanquet N, Wrston D, Erens R, Delbanco TL. National survey of hospital patients. *Br Med J* 1994;309:1542-6
 7. Banos JE, Bosch F. Specific problems of analgesic therapy in the average hospital patients . *Med Clin (Barc)* 1996;106:222-6. [google translator,Spanish]
 8. McQuay H, Moore A, Justins D. Treating acute pain in hospital. *Br Med J* 1997;314:1531-5.
 9. Mung'ayi V, Mwaka G, Thikra S. The prevalence of postoperative pain in the first 24 hours following day surgery at a tertiary hospital in Nairobi. *African Health Science* 2013;13(3).
 10. Sydow, FW. The influence of anesthesia and post operative analgesic management on lung function. *Acta Chir Scand* 1989;550(Suppl.):159-165.
 11. Wattwil, M. Postoperative pain relief and gastrointestinal motility. *Acta Chir Scand* 1989;550(Suppl.):140-145.
 12. Rowbotham D. Postoperative analgesia. *Aust Prescriber J* 1995;18:88-91.
 13. Torda T. Postoperative analgesia. *Aust Prescriber J* 1993;33:237-243.
 14. Paper Em, Brodie BB, Rovenstine EA. Postoperativepain: its use in the comparative evaluation of analgesics. *Surg* 1952;32:107-109.
 15. Clinical and Therapeutic. Round table: Good use of analgesics. *Therapy* 1992;47:471-9. [google translator,French]
 16. American Pain Society Quality of Case Committee.
 17. Quality improvement Marks RM, Sachar EJ. Undertreatment of medical inpatients with narcotic analgesics. *Ann Inter Med* 1973;78:173-181.
 18. Cohen FL. Postsurgical pain relief: patients` status and nurses` medication choices. *Pain* 1980;9:265-274.
 19. Shriwatankul K, Weiss OF, Alloza JL, Kelvie W, Weintraub M, Lasagna L. Analysis of narcotic analgesic usage in the treatment of postoperative pain *JAMA* 1983;250:926-9.
 20. Banos JE, Bosch F, Ortega F. Analgesic pain treatment in three hospitals. *Rev Clin Esp* 1989;184:177-181. [google translator,Spanish]
 21. Kuhn S, Cooke K, Collins M, Mucklow JC. Perceptions of pain relief after surgery. *Br Med J* 1990;108:136-140.
 22. Aguilera C, Arnau Jm, Bosch C. Study group on Postoperative analgesia clinical pharmacology Spanish sociedad. *Med clin (Barc)* 1997;108:136-140. [google translator,Spanish]
 23. Ready LB, Oden R, Chadwick HS, Benedetti C, Rooke GA, Caplan R, et al. Development of an anaesthesiology- based postoperative pain service. *Anesthesiol* 1988;68:100-106.
 24. Gould TH, Crosby DL, Harmer M, Llyod SM, Lunn JN, Ress GA, et al. Policy for controlling pain after surgery: effect of sequential changes in management. *Br Med J* 1992;305:1187-1193.
 25. Rewal N, Berggren L. Organization of acute pain services: a low cost model. *Pain* 1994;57:117-123.
 26. American Society of Anaesthesiologists Task force on Pain Management, Acute Pain Section. Practice guidelines for acute pain management in perioperative setting. *Anesthesiol* 1995;82:1071-1081.
 27. Meeting of the French Society Pharmacology guidelines for the treatment of acute pain and cancer pain. *JAMA* 1995;47:471-9.
 28. Kopf Andreas, Patel B. Nilesh. Guide of Pain Management in Low Resource Setting. International Association for the Study of Pain 2010;15-6.
 29. Chung F, Ritchie E, Su J. Postoperative pain in ambulatory surgery. *Anesth Analg* 1997;85(4):808-816.
 30. White PF. The role of non-opioid analgesic techniques in the management of pain after ambulatory surgery. *Anesth Analg* 2002;94(3):577-585.
 31. Sinatra S. Raymond, Ginsberg Brian. Acute Pain Management. Cambridge University Press. 2009.
 32. Breivic H, Allen SM, Rosslund LA, Romundstad L, Kvarstein G, Borchgrevink PC, et al. Assessment of Pain. *Brit J of Anes* 2008;101(1):17-24.
 33. Melzack R. The Mc Gill Questionnaire: Major properties and screening methods. *Pain* 1975;1:277-99.
 34. Becket J, Schwartz C, Saries-Baglana RN. Using Item Response Theory (IRT) for developing and evaluating the pain Impact Questionnaire (PIQ-6TM). *Pain Med* 2007;S129-44.
 35. Phillips S, Tapp H, Gift M, Duong M, Gelot S. Assessing the relationship between the level of pain control and patient satisfaction. *J Pain Res* 2003;6:683-9.
 36. Breivik EK, Bjo`rnsson GA, Skovlund E. A comparison of pain rating scales by sampling from clinical trial data. *Clin J Pain*

- 2000;16:22–8.
37. von Baeyer CL. Numerical rating scale for self-report of pain intensity in children and adolescent: Recent progress and further question. *Eur J Pain* 2009;1005-7.
 38. Langley GB, Sheppard H. The visual analogue scale: Its use in pain management, *Rheumatol Int* 1985;5:145-8.
 39. Kumar P, Tripathi L. Challenges in pain assessment: Pain intensity scales. *Indian J Pain* 2014;28:61-70
 40. Jensen MP, Karoly P, Braver S. Measurement of clinical pain intensity: a comparison of six methods. *Pain* 1986;27:117-126.
 41. William A, Hoggart B. Pain: a review of three commonly used pain rating scales. *J Clinical Nursing* 2004;14:798-804.
 42. Bijur PE, Latimer CT, Gallagher EJ. Validation of a verbally administered numerical rating scale of acute pain for use in the emergency department. *Academic Emergency Medicine* 2003;10:390–92.
 43. DeLoach LJ, Higgins MS, Caplan AB, Stiff JL. The visual analog scale in the immediate postoperative period: intrasubject variability and correlation with a numeric scale. *Anesthesia and Analgesia* 1988;86:102–6.
 44. Brewer SG. Massage of feet: pain control option. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Indian University, USA 2001.
 45. Sitepu N F. The effect of zikr meditation on post operative pain among Muslim patients undergoing abdominal surgery, Medan, Indonesia. Master Thesis, Prince of Songkla University, Thailand. 2009.
 46. Wang, H L, Keck J F. Foot and hand massage as an intervention for postoperative pain. *American Society for Pain Management Nursing* 2004;5:59-65.
 47. Zhou Y, Petpichetchian W, Kitrungrate L. Psychometric properties of pain intensity scales comparing among postoperative adult patients, elderly patients without and with mild cognitive impairment in china. *International Journal of Nursing Studies* 2011;48:449-57.
 48. Chanif, Petpichetchian W, Chongchareon W. Acute Postoperative Pain of Indonesian Patients after Abdominal Surgery. *Nurse Media Journal of Nursing* 2012;2(2):409-20.
 49. Gordon DB, Polomano RC, Pellino TA, Turk DC, McCracken LM, Sherwood G. et al. Revised American Pain Society Patient Outcome Questionnaire (APS-POQ-R) for quality improvement of pain management in hospitalized adults: preliminary psychometric evaluation. *J Pain* 2010;11(11):1172–86.
 50. Hanna MN, González-Fernández M, Barrett AD, Williams KA, Pronovost P. Does patient perception of pain control affect patient satisfaction across surgical units in a tertiary teaching hospital? *Am J Med Qual* 2012;27(5):411–16.
 51. Pellino TA, Ward SE. Perceived control mediates the relationship between pain severity and patient satisfaction. *J Pain Symptom Manage* 1998;15(2):110–116.
 52. Chung JW, Lui JC. Postoperative pain management: study of patients' level of pain and satisfaction with health care providers' responsiveness to their reports of pain. *Nurs Health Sci* 2003;5(1):13–21.
 53. Weis OF, Sriwatanakul K, Alloza J, Weintraub M, Lasagna L. Attitudes of patients, housestaff, and nurses toward postoperative analgesic care. *Anesth Analg* 1983;62(1):70–74.
 54. Donovan BD. Patient attitudes to postoperative pain relief. *Anaesth Intensive Care*. 1983;11(2):125–129.
 55. Brown C, Constance K, Bédard D, Purden M. Colorectal surgery patients' pain status, activities, satisfaction, and beliefs about pain and pain management. *Pain Manage Nurs* 2011. In press.
 56. Browne AL, Andrews R, Schug SA, Wood F. Persistent pain outcomes and patient satisfaction with pain management after burn injury. *Clin J Pain* 2011;27(2):136–145.
 57. Panteli V, Patistea E. Assessing patients' satisfaction and intensity of pain as outcomes in the management of cancer-related pain. *Eur J Oncol Nurs* 2007;11(5):424–433.
 58. Malouf J, Andi3n O, Torrubia R, Cañellas M, Baños JE. A survey of perceptions with pain management in Spanish inpatients. *J Pain Symptom Manage* 2006;32(4):361–371.
 59. Miaskowski C, Nichols R, Brody R, Synold T. Assessment of patient satisfaction utilizing the American Pain Society's Quality Assurance Standards on acute and cancer-related pain. *J Pain Symptom Manage* 1994;9(1):5–11.